

Banking Sector Regulation and Financial Intermediation in Nigeria

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This study investigated the impact of banking sector regulation on financial intermediation in Nigeria using secondary data from 1981 to 2023. The main focus of this study was examining the impact of monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio and loan-to-deposit ratio (measures of banking sector regulation) on financial intermediation (proxy by total deposit money banks' deposit, credit to the private sector, deposit money banks' lending to SMEs, and broad money supply). To achieve this, data was sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin. The effect of banking sector regulation on financial intermediation was examined in the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) framework. Other estimation tools employed were unit root testing and cointegration test. It was revealed from the result root test that the underlying series were mixed of order $I(0)$ and $I(1)$ and long run equilibrium relationship between banking sector regulation and financial intermediation was confirmed using the bound test. The ARDL results revealed that monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio and loan-to-deposit ratio had significant positive impact on total deposit money banks' deposit. Liquidity ratio had significant negative impact on credit to private sector, while the effect of loan-to-deposit ratio on credit to private sector was positive and significant. The study found that liquidity ratio and loan-to-deposit ratio are the major determinants of deposit money banks' lending to small and medium enterprises. An increase in monetary policy rate was found to have significant positive impact on broad money supply, as evidence showed that liquidity ratio had significant positive effect on broad money supply. From these empirical results, the study concludes that banking sector regulatory tool can be used to address financial intermediation. To enhance financial intermediation, the study recommends reduction in the monetary policy rate and liquidity ratio.

Keywords: Banking Regulation; Monetary Policy; Liquidity Ratio; Loan-to-deposit ratio

INTRODUCTION

The banking sector regulation in developing economies is traced to the financial sector reform in the late 1980s which was characterized by the implementation of interest rate deregulation and the opening of the capital account among others. It was intended to promote a sound financial system and build investors' confidence while providing incentives for attracting foreign investments in the banking sector. The insufficient supervisory framework due to the lack of an efficient risk asset database and information sharing system, as well

as a lack of commitments and abuse of duties on the part of the financial institutions, have all played a significant role in interfering with the operations of banks, insurance companies, and securities firms. Notably, macro- and microprudential policy collectively seek to maintain the financial system's stability by assisting it in effectively allocating resources to the real economy.

Specifically, microprudential regulation is based on the Basel II capital requirements, risk management standards, and other prudential standards such those

relating to provisioning, asset classification, and significant exposure guidelines. A number of Basel III provisions significantly improve microprudential rules and would make individual banks and banking groups safer. Basel III's understanding of the need to address systemic risk, which it addresses through macroprudential rules, is a novel aspect. According to Sihna (2023), the banking regulation's features included removing general policy restrictions on banks' ability to carry out their fundamental tasks, promoting universal banking, allowing non-bank financial entities to engage in financial intermediation, giving financial markets more weight when allocating resources, and enhancing financial market integration.

Furthermore, an important feature of financial regulation in developed countries is the exclusive focus on institution-specific regulation. As outlined in the Geithner Report of 2009, no regulator in the US considered it as part of its responsibility to safeguard the country's financial system and economy as a whole. This is because the existing bank regulation focused mainly on safeguarding the subsidiary bank than on comprehensive regulation of the entire industry. The banking sector regulation in developing economies is traced to the financial sector reform in the late 1980s which was characterized by the implementation of interest rate deregulation and opening of the capital account among others. It was intended to promote a sound financial system and build investors' confidence while providing incentives for attracting foreign investments in the banking sector.

In Nigeria, the Banks and Other Financial Institutions Act (BOFIA) of 2007 empowered the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) to supervise and regulate banks and other financial institutions. The Act has birthed the promulgation of financial legislation to guide the activities of key players in the banking sector. According to Akujobi, Anyanwu and Eke (2023), the BOFIA was primarily intended to guide sound financial practice in the economy. In addition, Uffot (2003) and Olorushola (2003) identify banking regulation as a veritable tool to guide financial institutions to follow international best practices and adhere to laid-down rules that ultimately bring about sanity in the financial industry and the economy at large.

As the apex monetary authority in Nigeria, the CBN oversees the regulation of the banking practice by issuing and granting licenses to banks to carry on the business of banking and supervise banks and other financial institutions. It is also empowered to issue guidelines and circulars relating to its responsibility to deposit money banks, foreign exchange market, and other financial institutions while creating enabling environments for banks and other financial institutions to deliver effective services in a resourceful and sustainable manner. Aside from the CBN, the Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) has the responsibility of insuring all deposit liabilities of licensed banks and other deposit financial institutions operating in Nigeria in the event of

failure of the financial institutions. This helps to strengthen the regulatory framework in the banking sector. In addition, under the Companies and Allied Matters Act, the Corporate Affairs Commission has regulatory powers over all registered companies in Nigeria including banks and other financial institutions particularly in respect of certain statutory filings required to be made by them. The Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) is saddled with the responsibility of enforcing compliance with accounting, auditing, corporate governance and financial reporting standards in Nigeria. As public companies, banks and other financial institutions come within the regulatory oversight of the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC). It is also worthy of note that the SEC is generally responsible for the regulation of banks listed on the Nigerian Exchange. It is important to note that a sound and stable regulatory framework is imperative for effective financial intermediation. This is also acknowledged in later studies to sustain public confidence, without which the banks' ability to mobilise and deploy savings as the means to promote economic growth would be eroded. However, the extent to which banking regulation promoted banking sector intermediation in Nigeria has remained an issue of contention.

On one hand, some scholars (Oluseun, 2020) argue that prudential regulations are imperative for the safety and soundness of the financial system which creates opportunities for fostering public confidence. On the other hand, Alley (2022), El-Mubarak, Mustapha and Hassan (2021), Enemona (2021) and Uddin (2021) posit that regulatory inefficiency characterises the banking system given its underdeveloped nature. In view of the growing contentions on the efficiency of banking regulation, this study shall examine how the banking sector regulation has affected the level of financial intermediation in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria, banking regulations which cut across six broad and integrated activities of monetary policy regulation, safety and soundness regulation, credit allocation regulation, investor protection regulation and entry regulation have remained at the forefront of the banking sector development and overall improvement in the financial system. It is adjudged to play a crucial role in financial deepening and economic development through the process of financial intermediation.

The regulations mainly situate around the quality of risk assets held by banks, and compliance with important ratios including the liquidity ratio, cash reserve ratio, and capital adequacy ratio, in addition to the management quality, and other aspects of corporate governance. However, the challenge of ensuring efficient and effective banking regulation to foster sound financial practice in the Nigerian economy in accordance with BOFIA has

remained very problematic in the past two decades.

It is worrisome that poor regulatory framework and ineffective risk asset database and information sharing systems have characterized banking regulations in Nigeria. This poses a threat of bank distress and liquidation. Umar (2015) outlines the inadequate supervisory framework, unreliable risk asset database and information sharing system, lack of obligations and abuse of duties on the part of financial institutions as barriers to sound financial practice in Nigeria. Again, it is pertinent to note that the regulatory framework in the banking sector has been characterized by widespread policy inconsistency as regulatory authorities, especially the CBN and NDIC have remained largely inconsistent in their policy design and implementation. Idehen (2024) posits that regulatory policies have frequently undergone drastic changes since Nigeria gained independence in 1960. This has continued to erode public confidence in the government's competence.

It is also worrisome that successive monetary authorities in Nigeria have demonstrated pronounced levels of policy discontinuity as they tend to abandon the policy initiatives of their predecessors. Atuka (2008) opines that a new government in Nigeria is often associated with new policies and the old government tends to fade with her old policies. This often promotes regulatory inefficiency which undermines the actualization of the policy goal with the emergence of a largely unregulated shadow financial system. The intended and desired policy effects of banking regulations have continued to be threatened by frequent government interventions in addition to the pervasive policy contradictions. This tends to undermine the CBN's anticipated autonomy in the conduct of monetary policy and overall banking supervision, which renders the decision-making process and results more unpredictable.

Despite the increasing recognition of the need for a robust regulatory structure to rectify market imperfections in the banking sector, it is worrisome that regulatory risks have continued to persist, thereby posing a threat to monetary policy implementation, soundness of the financial and intermediation role of deposit money banks. Every bank has evolved into an organisation that harms the economy due to widespread regulatory inefficiency, lack of accountability and transparency. This has raised doubts about the capability of the monetary authorities to adequately regulate the activities of banks and other institutions across the country. Accordingly, this study seeks to examine how various forms of banking regulations have affected financial intermediation in Nigeria.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the effect of banking sector regulation on the level of financial intermediation in Nigeria from the period of 1981-2023. The specific

objectives of this study are to:

- i. examine the effect of the monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio and loan-to-deposit ratio on total deposit money banks' deposits;
- ii. ascertain the effect of the monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio and loan-to-deposit ratio on credit to the private sector;
- iii. examine the effect of monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio and loan-to-deposit ratio on deposit money banks' lending to SMEs; and
- iv. determine the effect of monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio and loan-to-deposit ratio on the ratio of the broad money supply to GDP in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Review

Banking regulation

Regulation can be described as an official law enforced on people or groups of people by the state or by several officials. Regulation is seen as a body of particular regulations enforced either by the state or an industry-wide agreement that regulates the operations of the industry organizations (Gummi,2015).According to Llwellyn 1986, bank regulation is described as a body of particular regulations or accepted behavior either enforced by the government, other external or self-imposed by the industry's explicit or implicit contract limiting Deposit Money Banks ' operations and operations (lyade, 2006).Bank regulation acts as a core for stabilizing and ensuring the banking system's effectiveness. According to Chude and Chude (2014), banking regulation can be described as supervising and controlling banking operations with the objective of defending depositors ' value and ensuring the banking industries efficient functioning. Regulation is the government's rational response to these fresh mistakes in the economy.

Failure to respond would lead in either excessive risk taking by financial institutions or monopoly power growth and development, which is a natural economic consequence of such market conditions. Ultimately, with this view, banking regulation is justified by an appeal to the presence of market failure, without which such regulation would be pointless and Pareto would achieve optimal allocation of funds. However, when considering banking regulation, there is an extra level of complexity. This significantly changes the data landscape and makes it harder to achieve Pareto efficiency (Stiglitz (1994).

The 1952 Banking Ordinance implemented minimum requirements for disbursement of capital and reserve funds. The 1958 Central Bank Act and 1959 Banking Ordinance were enacted. The banking law was further

strengthened with the enactment of the banking decree of 1969. This consolidated previous banking legislation; lifted the minimum paid-up capital requirement.

Banking regulation in Nigeria deals primarily with policies and quasi-legal structures produced in the form of bye legislation, codes, acts and decrees developed during the military government (Ajayi, 2015). Regarding banking, regulation can be described as bank regulators' procedures and steps for controlling, regulating and supervising banks' operations. In Nigeria, there are bank regulators, Nigeria's Central Bank, which is banks' apex regulatory authority, and the Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC).

Measurement of the quality of banking regulation

According to the Basel Committee (1999), achieving a sound banking system by means of excellent regulation is not an end in itself because it also contributes to macroeconomic development by enhancing resource allocation effectiveness. Neyaptı and Dincer (2004) suggested a list of criteria based on banking legislation for measuring the quality of bank regulation and oversight (RS). They are;

Capital requirements: The minimum requirement for licensing capital, limitations on holding risky assets and constraints on capital purchases all plan to fulfill the objective of restricting banks' excessive risk-taking (Cleassens, 1997).

Lending: Establishing credit standards is critical to ensuring the health of the bank. Therefore, price, interest, and exchange rate risk constraints in lending, the existence of borrowers' controls, the decision to lend to large borrowers and executives, and public lending restrictions all provide significant data for regulatory measurement. Detailed data on each of the above enables to define and monitor the banking system's credit risk.

Ownership structure: Information on shareholder economic status and shareholder transfer is all oriented towards achieving and maintaining prudent banking system economic norms. Directors and executives: qualifying constraints on bank executives and executives are intended to assess the competence, trustworthiness and responsibility of bank management, which is important for prudence in banking operations.

Reporting-recording requirements: Information on working plan control structures and scope of details on on-site oversight and; coverage and frequency of reporting demands all enable close surveillance of the results of banks. In addition, they all assist to create sound company procedures and discourage fraud, the imprudent behavior of banks and the taking of unnecessary danger.

Corrective action: In the event of inadequate regulation resulting in the accumulation of poor loans, illiquidity or

bank insolvency, the supervisory officer may intervene in various ways, such as assigning a conservator or liquidation trustee, offering credit, removing the license, imposing penalties or limiting banking operations.

Supervision: The level of data given in both supervisory reports and the supervisor's rights and responsibilities helps to assess the efficiency of monitoring the execution of regulatory standards.

THEORETICAL LITERATURE

Banking Regulation Theory

The theory of banking regulation was proposed by Stigler (1971), and it is based on the assumption that regulation arises solely to advance the overall public interest by correcting market failures. In accordance with the theory, in contrast to public interest theory, government intervention does not seek to correct market inefficiencies but (following capture theory) rather accommodates the notion that regulation exists to promote the interests of politically effective groups (Stigler 1971). The following authors summarise economic regulation theory in the banking industry: According to Stigler (1971), regulations are some policies that govern the market based on the strength of the government's power.

Meanwhile, Chang (1997) argues that the regulation is a service to the community with the goal of efficiency. Another opinion came from Demirguc-Kunt and Detragiache (1998), who improved the regulatory environment that could prevent a banking crisis. According to Taswan (2010), the banking industry needs regulation in this regard because banking institutions, besides aiming for national business, also mandate welfare for people. Regulation would force banks to act fairly, thereby increasing people's prosperity. The interests of stakeholders. The bank is run by the people for the people. Stakeholders' interests take precedence because they have a vested interest in a bank's survival; a bank is a trusted institution. Stakeholders are comfortable investing in banks because they have faith in the bank's management.

However, if the bank fails or is liquidated, it may trigger a domino effect that disrupts the national banking system and the national economy. According to Backer (1983), regulatory decisions are not disinterested but reflect particular interests, and bank regulation can be understood as the result of the successive impact of pressure from interest groups.

Furthermore, According to Dendawijaya (2009), the bank's regulation aims to: safety is to prevent market failure and public deposit withdrawals that result in a loss to the bank; stability is related to the goal of macroeconomic stabilisation or maintaining macroeconomic stability; and structure is the issue of competition and efficiency in the bank. To be considered for capital regulation, banks, particularly SIBs, must

meet risk-weighted capital requirements.

According to economic regulation theory, risk-weighted capital requirements are acquired by the banking industry for its benefit because, under the risk-weight approach, SIBs can manipulate the capital required to be held for funding propositions. According to Stigler (1971), on the demand side of the banking industry, the SIBs ask for more regulation (an internal ratings-based approach) that does not seek to correct market failures but rather to promote the interests of the politically effective group, namely, the SIBs. Although the above-mentioned example might be a possible explanation for the theory of economic regulation in the banking sector, further academic research is necessary to make such a determination.

Theories explaining regulation as an efficient solution to market failures have been criticised from various perspectives over the years. First, the market failure theory, which is at the heart of public interest regulatory theories, has been criticized. Second, empirical research is said to have invalidated the hypothesis that government regulation is efficient or effective. In contrast to this criticism, it has been argued in third place that it is impossible to test or refute public interest regulatory theories. Finally, it has been argued that public interest theories are insufficient because they do not account for the formation of public preferences and the translation of these preferences into welfare-maximizing regulatory measures.

Commercial Loan Theory

This theory was proposed by Moulton (1915) and is based on the assumption that a commercial bank should advance only short-term self-liquidating productive loans to business firms. In accordance with the theory, self-liquidating loans are those which are meant to finance the production and movement of goods through the successive stages of production, storage, transportation, and distribution. It is the oldest theory of liquidity management. It seeks to match short-term profit motives with short-term obligations of making depositors' funds available when needed. The doctrine is buttressed by Onoh (2002). He is of the view that for the management and application of funds (liquidity) to be effective, the tenor of funds (sourced from deposits and other sources) must be matched with the tenor of assets (i.e., loans and advances to customers, etc.). This theory has been subjected to various criticisms, such as Dodds (1982) and Nwankwo (1992). From their point of view, the major limitation is that the theory is inconsistent with the demands of economic development, especially for developing countries since it excludes long-term loans, which are the engine of growth. The theory assumes that repayment from the self-liquidating assets of the bank would be sufficient to provide for liquidity. This ignores the fact that seasonal deposit withdrawals and meeting

credit requests could affect the liquidity position adversely. Furthermore, in terms of liquidity consideration, the theory fails to reflect the normal stability of demand deposits.

Empirical Literature

Toby (2023) employed four regression models to examine how bank management ratios affected rural lending and small business finance in Nigeria between 1992 and 2022. The time series data obtained from the CBN Statistical Bulletin was used for the analysis. The study found evidence of a critical gap in bank intermediation in the rural area and SME sectors. Specifically, the results revealed that a significantly positive relationship exists between rural loan-to-deposit ratio and aggregate loan-to-deposit ratio. It was also evident from the coefficient of determination that 84.02 percent of the variations in rural loan-to-deposit ratio were explained by changes in the bank management variables. The results further showed that the bank management variables varied negatively with the ratio of loans to SMEs. The study also found no evidence to buttress the claim that banks are dealing significantly with the problem of information asymmetries by improving their lending to the SMEs in Nigeria. based on the findings, the study concluded that banks seem not to live up to expectation in terms of their role of financing the entrepreneurship innovation. Thus, it is recommended that monetary policy should prioritize compliance with prudential standards, deepen rural financing and promote the mandatory credit allocation to SMEs in Nigeria.

Olofinlade and Azeez (2023) used the unrestricted structural VAR method to empirically examine the composite effects of monetary policy on bank lending and economic performance in Nigeria between 1986 and 2022. This study employed secondary data sourced from the CBN and National Bureau of statistics. The results of the estimation showed that monetary policies on banks' lending and economic performance were significantly correlated. Individually, the result revealed that money supply, monetary policy rate, exchange rate, and bank lending have positive and significant effect on economic performance while inflation had negative but insignificant effect on economic performance. On the basis of the findings, the study recommended that government should put forward proactive measures and programs that can significantly bring down the increasing exchange rate and inflation rate to attract more investments.

Orji, et al. (2022) used vector error correction model to empirically determine the channels of transmission through which cash reserve ratio impacts on credit to micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs).. Quarterly data ranging from 2001 to 2017 were also utilized in the analysis. The study found that cash reserve ratio indirectly impacts credit to MSMEs through liquidity ratio and lending interest rate as its channels of

transmission. It is worthy to note that, as liquidity ratio has a positive significant impact on credit to MSMEs, lending interest rate has a negative but significant impact on credit to MSMEs. To boost economic productivity in developing economies, the study recommends that the monetary authorities reduce the cash reserve ratio in order to increase commercial banks' liquidity. The study also recommended that government should appropriate and monitor the judicious disbursement of interest-free loans/credit to MSMEs through banks, especially development banks.

Dallis (2023) examined the challenges of financial intermediation in the Nigerian Banking System in the wake of the twenty first century. The study specifically assessed the role and impacts of information technology on the banking sector. A quantitative approach was followed for the analysis and the results showed that information technology has facilitated financial intermediation, through cost reduction and timely delivery of financial services.

However, the study revealed that most banks in Nigeria are facing keen competition both within and outside the shores of Nigeria such as mass movement of high-asset based banks towards efficiency thereby combining their advantages of big assets with efficiency which further expands their market and narrows those of the banks with relatively lower assets. Besides, there is the problem of financial fraud aided" by information technology. Given the findings, the study recommended that Nigerians banks should invest in both information technology and human capital to brace up to the challenges of the New World Order.

Abere, Obarafo and Adewole (2020) examined the effect of monetary policy on allocation of loan and advances to small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria from the period of 1992 to 2017. The study utilized secondary data obtained from the CBN and National Bureau of Statistic (NBS) and introduces commercial banks loan and advances as the dependent variable while money supply, interest rate, monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio of commercial banks, inflation rate and exchange rate are the independent variables. The study relied on the Ordinary Least Square regression as data analysis and found that monetary policy rate and exchange rate were positively related to commercial bank loans and advances to small and medium scale enterprises. On the other hand, money supply, liquidity ratio and inflation rate negatively affect commercial banks loans and advances to SMEs in Nigeria. Given the findings, the study recommended for government to reduce monetary policy rate thereby making commercial banks loan and advances accessible by small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria.

Using multiple regression method, Uwazie and Aina (2022) investigated the cause and effect of monetary policy variables on commercial banks loans and advances in Nigeria for the period 1980-2021. The

study utilized time series data from the CBN Statistical Bulletin and found that there was a causal relationship between monetary policy variables and commercial banks loans and advances in Nigeria within the period. It was also established that there exists cause and effect between commercial bank loans and advances and the monetary policy variables. Money supply had a significant effect on commercial bank loans and advances while, commercial bank loans and advances was found to have significant effect on exchange rate. The study concluded that increase in liquidity ratio, inflation rate and exchange rate bring about a decrease in the commercial bank loans and advances.

Philips, Mbanasor and Osuala (2022) used Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS) to assess long term implication of monetary policy variables on banks' credit supply to small and medium scale enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria over the period 1995-2021. The study used the time series data obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical bulletin and the financial statements of the banks used. The estimated FMOLS model showed that policies on interest rate and liquidity ratio were negatively and positively significant to credit supply given to SMEs. Thus, the study concluded that monetary policy measures play outstanding in driving SMEs performance in Nigeria.

Literature Gap

Arising from the foregoing review of the theoretical and empirical literature, it is evident that several studies have been conducted on this subject matter in different time and space. To begin with, this study extended the content scope of the previous studies by providing an in-depth review of more specific theories with a focus on banking regulation theory and theory of banking supervision and enforcement, theory of prudential regulation. This deepened the understanding on the theoretical link between banking sector supervision and intermediary role of banks, which were ignored by other studies as they focused on the generic review of the theoretical literature.

In addition, this study shall improve on the previous studies by utilizing a broader measure of banking sector regulation based on breadth of coverage and depth regulation in the banking sector in Nigeria in accordance with the BOFIA. This shall make meaningful improvements to previous studies by providing more encompassing insights into the banking sector regulation and how they affect the process of financial intermediation in Nigeria. Additionally, this study shall integrate both the deposit and lending aspects of financial intermediation which is narrowly measured in the previous studies which relied mostly on the lending aspect. This shall create an opportunity for a clear understanding of the depth and coverage of the financial intermediation process.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

An ex-post-facto research design was used because of the nature of this investigation. Ex-post-facto research design is a sort of research design where the empirical study begins after the fact without the researcher's intervention.

Model Specification

In accordance with the specific objectives of this study, four multiple regression models shall be adopted to examine how banking sector regulation has affected the financial intermediation process in Nigeria. Essentially, the banking regulation variables such as monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio and cash reserve ratio shall serve as the independent variables whereas the financial intermediation variables such as the total deposit money banks' deposits, credit to the private sector, deposit money banks' lending to SMEs and broad money supply to GDP in Nigeria are the dependent variables. The functional specifications of the models are provided as:

$$TBD_t = f(MPR, LQR, LDT) \quad (3.1)$$

$$CPS_t = f(MPR, LQR, LDT) \quad (3.2)$$

$$LSME_t = f(MPR, LQR, LDT) \quad (3.3)$$

$$RBS_t = f(MPR, LQR, LDT) \quad (3.4)$$

Where: TBD = total deposit money banks' deposits

CPS = credit to the private sector

LSME = deposit money banks' lending to SMEs

RBS = broad money supply to GDP

MPR = monetary policy rate

LQR = liquidity ratio

LDT = loan-to-deposit ratio

However, the specification of the econometrics models of the functional models equations are provided as follows:

Model 1:

$$TBD_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MPR_t + \beta_2 LQR_t + \beta_3 LDT_t + U_{1t} \quad (3.5)$$

Model 2:

$$CPS_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MPR_t + \beta_2 LQR_t + \beta_3 LDT_t + U_{1t} \quad (3.6)$$

Model 3:

$$LSME_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MPR_t + \beta_2 LQR_t + \beta_3 LDT_t + U_{1t} \quad (3.7)$$

Model 4:

$$RBS_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 MPR_t + \beta_2 LQR_t + \beta_3 LDT_t + U_{1t} \quad (3.8)$$

Where: β_0 = constant parameter

$\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = coefficients of the independent variables

U_{1t} = random error term

In addition, the vector error correction models (VECM) for this study are specified as follows:

Model 1:

$$TBD_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta TBD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{1t} \quad (3.9)$$

$$MPR_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta TBD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{2t} \quad (3.10)$$

$$LQR_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta TBD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{3t} \quad (3.11)$$

$$LDT_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta TBD_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{4t} \quad (3.12)$$

Model 2:

$$CPS_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta CPS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{1t} \quad (3.13)$$

$$MPR_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta CPS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{2t} \quad (3.14)$$

$$LQR_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta CPS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{3t} \quad (3.15)$$

$$LDT_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta CPS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{4t} \quad (3.16)$$

Model 3:

$$LSME_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta LSME_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{1t} \quad (3.17)$$

$$MPR_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta LSME_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{2t} \quad (3.18)$$

$$LQR_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta LSME_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{3t} \quad (3.19)$$

$$LDT_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta LSME_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{4t} \quad (3.20)$$

Model 4:

$$RBS_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta RBS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{1t} \quad (3.21)$$

$$MPR_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta RBS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{2t} \quad (3.22)$$

$$LQR_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta RBS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{3t} \quad (3.23)$$

$$LDT_t = \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{11} \Delta RBS_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{12} \Delta MPR_{1t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{13} \Delta LQR_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \beta_{14} \Delta LDT_{t-i} + \alpha_1 ECM_{t-1} + U_{4t} \quad (3.24)$$

Where: Δ = first difference operator
 q = optimal lag notation

β_{11} and β_{14} = vector of coefficients of the regressors

α_1 = error correction coefficient

e_{1t} and e_{4t} = vectors for the white noise error terms

existing theories and later studies, was a major driving force for the choice of the VECM.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Descriptive Statistics**

The descriptive analysis which covered the four proxies

Method of Data Collection

This study shall rely on secondary data from existing documentary sources. Specifically, time series data on financial intermediation shall be sourced from the CBN Statistical Bulletin. In addition, data on banking sector regulation shall be obtained from the National Bureau of Statistics and CBN Statistical Bulletin.

Method of Data Analysis

In this study, the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) was applied for the analysis. The popularity of non-stationarity among time series, as contained in the

of financial intermediation process [total deposit money banks' deposit (TBD), credit to the private sector (CPS) expressed as a percentage of gross domestic product, deposit money banks' lending to SMEs (LSME) measured as a percentage of total credit, broad money supply to GDP (RBS)] and the three indexes of banking sector regulation [monetary policy rate (MPR), liquidity ratio, and loan-to-deposit ratio (LDT)] document that a total of NGN2,020.080 is expected to be deposit each year with the deposit money banks in Nigeria. This average volume of deposits with deposit money banks in Nigeria fluctuated over the forty-one (41) years period of

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of Series Employed

	TBD	CPS	LSME	RBS	MPR	LQR	LDT
Mean	2020.080	11.4731	5.5742	15.4197	13.0000	49.0695	67.4826
Median	448.0214	8.0900	0.9190	12.7800	13.0000	46.2300	66.9000
Max.	6388.651	22.7500	27.0355	24.9000	26.0000	104.2000	96.8200
Min.	4.8809	5.8100	0.0700	8.4600	6.0000	26.3900	37.5600
Std. Dev	2521.252	5.5295	7.1861	5.3543	3.9591	14.6681	13.5089
Skewness	0.7474	0.6876	1.2322	0.5445	0.7343	1.4638	-0.2094
Kurtosis	1.7913	1.7184	3.7646	1.6258	4.5427	6.3999	2.6056
JB.	6.3136	6.0370	8.3229	5.2523	7.7506	34.3902	0.5655
Prob.	0.0425	0.0488	0.0155	0.0723	0.0207	0.0000	0.7536
Obs.	41	41	30	41	41	41	41

Source: Author's compilation (2024)

investigation. The minimum deposit made by Nigerians in their savings and current accounts held with deposit money banks was NGN4.8809 billion and the volume of deposit during the period peaked at N6,388.651 billion.

As a percentage of gross domestic product, credit distributed to the private sector during the period averaged 11.4731 percent. With credit to private sector as percentage of gross domestic product (GDP) employed in economics to gauge the degree of financial deepening in a country, the average value of 11.4731 percent suggest that the Nigerian financial system is underdeveloped, and this could have serious implication for credit mobilization, increase credit rationing and cause a spike in interest rate. Credit to the private sector, as a percentage of GDP, dipped to 5.8100 percent, while peaking at 22.75 percent. The peaked value of 22.75 percent also substantiates earlier claim that the financial institutions in Nigeria is underdeveloped, with implication for efficient credit allocation, effectiveness of monetary policy and enhancing economic growth.

As a percentage of total credit disbursed by deposit money banks (DMBs) in Nigeria, the study observed that only 5.5742 percents are disbursed to small and medium enterprises (SMEs). Such meagre proportion of total credit to small and medium enterprises has potential of weakening economic growth and could have severe implications for financial intermediation, as small and medium enterprises has been adjudged to be an engine of economic growth. Over the duration of the study, credit allocation to small and medium enterprises rose from a minimum of 0.07 percent of total credit to a maximum of 27.0355 percent of total DMBs credit. During the period of the study, broad money supply in the economy averaged 15.4197 percent of gross domestic product. The volume of money in circulation in the Nigerian economy was not less than 8.46 percent of GDP, peaking at 24.90 percent of GDP. The expected monetary policy rate was 13.00 percent annually.

For the period of the investigation, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) reduced her policy rate to 6 percent and hiked her benchmark rate to double digit figure of 26 percent. With liquidity ratio utilized as tools by the apex bank to regulate the banking sector, the expected liquidity

ratio was 49.0695 percent. The study observed seasonally fluctuation in the liquidity ratio, as the minimum liquidity ratio was 26.39 percent. During the period of investigation, liquidity ratio rose to 104.2 percent. As documented in Table 4.2, the mean value of loan-to-deposit ratio was 67.4826 percent, indicating that 67.4826 percent of total deposit is expected to be allocated as loans to the private sector. This volume of credit as percentage of total deposit peaked at 96.82 percent and declined to 37.56 percent during the period of the study.

The degree of variability in the series was also analysis, as provided by the standard deviation. This statistical method provides information on how disperse each observation of a series is from the mean of the distribution, providing insight into the degree of variability. Table 4.2 document high variability in total deposit money banks' deposit (TBD), credit to the private sector (CPS) expressed as a percentage of gross domestic product, deposit money banks' lending to SMEs (LSME) measured as a percentage of total credit, broad money supply to GDP (RBS), liquidity ratio, and loan-to-deposit ratio (LDT). This draws from the computed standard deviation for the series which were NGN2521.252 billion for total deposit money banks' deposit, 5.5295 percent for credit to private sector, 7.1861 percent for loan to small and medium scale enterprises, 5.3543 percent for broad money supply to GDP, 14.6681 percent for liquidity ratio, and 13.5089 percent for loan-to-deposit ratio. The skewness statistic indicates that total deposit money banks' deposit (TBD), credit to the private sector (CPS) expressed as a percentage of gross domestic product, deposit money banks' lending to SMEs (LSME) measured as a percentage of total credit, broad money supply to GDP (RBS), monetary policy rate (MPR), and liquidity ratio (LQR) are positively skewed, indicating upward movement in the distribution of these series. The study observed decreasing trend in the loan-to-deposit ratio (LDT), suggested by the skewness statistics of -0.2094. Based off the kurtosis statistics, the study observed that deposit money banks' lending to SMEs (LSME), monetary policy rate (MPR), and liquidity ratio (LQR) are leptokurtic, as their respective kurtosis values

Table 4.2: Result of Unit Root Test

Variables	Panel I: ADF			Panel II: PP			Remark I(d)
	Level	1 st Diff.	C-Value	Level	1 st Diff.	C-Value	
$\ln TBD_t$	-1.4741	-3.6454***	-2.9389	-1.1921	-3.6601***	-2.9369	I(1)
CPS_t	-1.0741	-5.8481***	-2.9369	-0.9565	-6.9231***	-2.9369	I(1)
$LSME_t$	-4.5286***	-	-2.9677	-4.9871***	-	-2.9677	I(0)
RBS_t	-0.8065	-5.7685***	-2.9369	-0.6212	-6.0392***	-2.9369	I(1)
MPR_t	-3.3345**	-	-2.9369	-3.2953**	-	-2.9369	I(0)
LQR_t	-3.5532**	-	-2.9369	-3.5532**	-	-2.9369	I(0)
LDT_t	-4.8110***	-	-2.9434	-3.0895**	-	-2.9369	I(0)

Source: Author computation (2024)

of 3.7646, 4.5427, and 6.3999 are higher than 3. total deposit money banks' deposit (TBD), credit to the private sector (CPS), broad money supply to GDP (RBS), and loan-to-deposit ratio (LDT) are considered platykurtic, as their respective kurtosis values of 1.7913, 1.7184, 1.6258, and 2.6056 are less than 3.

As documented in Table 4.2, majority of the series are not normally distributed. Specifically, the null hypothesis of normal distribution was rejected for total deposit money banks' deposit (TBD), credit to the private sector (CPS), deposit money banks' lending to SMEs (LSME), monetary policy rate (MPR), and liquidity ratio. Loan-to-deposit ratio (LDT) and broad money supply to GDP (RBS) was found to be normally distributed.

Unit Root Analysis

The result of the unit root conducted on each series as presented in Table 4.2 is partitioned into two panels of Panel I and Panel II. The unit root test results conducted using the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) method was reported in Panel I and the test results obtained using the Phillip-Perron (PP) method was documented in Panel II. In both panels, the study reported the test statistics and the associated critical values at 5 percent level of significance. The study adopted the two unit root test methods for confirmatory purposes and also for the diverse approach to unit root testing. The augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) method follows a parametric approach in testing for unit root, while the Phillip-Perron (PP) method adopted a non-parametric approach for unit root testing.

Table 4.3 document uniform report on the degree of integration of total deposit money banks' deposit (TBD), credit to the private sector (CPS), and broad money supply (RBS) by both the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillip-Perron (PP) methods. When total deposit money banks' deposit (TBD), credit to the private sector (CPS), and broad money supply (RBS) were subjected to unit root testing using the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) approach, the three series were found to contain unit root in their level form. The non-stability of these series in

their level form was confirmed following unit root testing performed using the Phillip-Perron (PP) approach. With the series [total deposit money banks' deposit (TBD), credit to the private sector (CPS), and broad money supply (RBS)] unstable in their level form, the study carried out first differencing and then subjected the first differenced series to unit root testing. As shown in Panel I and II, the first differenced series of total deposit money banks' deposit (TBD), credit to the private sector (CPS), and broad money supply (RBS) were found to be stable, indicating they are first difference stationary, or I(1) series.

The degree of integration of deposit money banks' lending to SMEs (LSME) measured as a percentage of total credit, monetary policy rate (MPR), liquidity ratio, and loan-to-deposit ratio (LDT) were found to be I(0) or stationary in level form, as the respective test statistics for the series were higher than the 5 percent critical values, in absolute term. The stability of deposit money banks' lending to SMEs (LSME) measured as a percentage of total credit, monetary policy rate (MPR), liquidity ratio, and loan-to-deposit ratio (LDT) in level form was confirmed using both the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillip-Perron (PP) methods. From the results of the unit root, the study concluded that the series order of integrations that are not identical, but mixed, that is, the series are I(0) and I(1) series. Guided by this, the study applied the Pesaran, et al., (2001) bound test over the Engle and Granger (1987) two-step residual based to test if the series in the models share similar stochastic trends.

Cointegration Test

The null hypothesis experimented by the bound test is that there is no level relationship among monetary policy rate (MPR), liquidity ratio, loan-to-deposit ratio (LDT), and total deposit money banks' deposit (TBD). In testing the null hypothesis, the calculated F-statistics is compared with the upper bound, or I(1), critical value at 5 percent level of significance. The null hypothesis of no long run relationship among the variables in the model is rejected

Table 4.3: Bound Test Result

Model	Optimal Lag Length	F-Statistics	Cointegration
$lntbs = f(mpr, lqr, ldt)$	(2, 0, 0, 1)	4.618773***	Null hypothesis: No levels relationship
Significant Level	I(0)	I(1)	
10%	2.37	3.20	
5%	2.79	3.67	
2.5%	3.15	4.08	
1%	3.65	4.66	

Note: *, ** and *** denote significance at 10%, 5% and 1% level, respectively.

Source: Author's computation (2024)

Table 4.5: Long Run and Short Run ECM Results

Dependent Variable: $lnTBD_t$				
Part A: Long Run Results				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t – Stats	Prob.
MPR_t	0.7662**	0.3234	2.3688	0.0237
LQR_t	0.2713***	0.0590	4.5914	0.0001
LDT_t	0.1076**	0.0436	2.4646	0.0189
C	-5.4917	30.0698	-0.1826	0.8562
Part B: Short Run Results				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t – Stats	Prob.
$D(lnTBD_{t-1})$	0.4747***	0.1335	3.5560	0.0012
$D(LDT_t)$	-0.0029	0.0019	-1.4636	0.1530
ECM_{t-1}	-0.0102***	0.0032	-3.1486	0.0035
$R^2 = 0.3360$		$Adjusted R^2 = 0.2991$		

Note: *, ** and *** denote significance at 10%, 5% and 1% level.

Long Run and Short Run ECM Results

Dependent Variable: CPS_t				
Part A: Long Run Results				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t – Stats	Prob.
MPR_t	-0.3254*	0.1642	-1.9814	0.0562
LQR_t	-0.3485**	0.1282	2.7182	0.0105
LDT_t	0.0632**	0.0235	2.6871	0.0113
C	-77.8566	250.1560	-0.3112	0.7578
Part B: Short Run Results				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t – Stats	Prob.
$D(MPR_t)$	0.1425	0.1017	1.4008	0.1715
$D(MPR_{t-1})$	0.1982*	0.1065	1.8606	0.0726
$D(LQR_t)$	-0.0355	0.0242	-1.4678	0.1526
$D(LQR_{t-1})$	-0.0457*	0.0228	-2.0006	0.0546
ECM_{t-1}	-0.0373**	0.0153	-2.4268	0.0214
$R^2 = 0.2618$		$Adjusted R^2 = 0.1749$		

Note: *, ** and *** denote significance at 10%, 5% and 1% level.

if the calculated F-statistics is higher than the 5 percent critical value. Cointegrating relationship among the variables is rejected whenever the calculated F-statistics is less than the I(1) 5 percent critical value. The cointegration test is inconclusive when the F-statistics value is higher than the lower bound critical value, but less than the upper bound 5 percent critical value.

As shown in Table 4.4, the study observed that the calculated F-statistics of 4.618773 is greater than the upper bound 5 percent critical value of 3.67. On the strength of this, the null hypothesis no level relationship among the interest variables was rejected and the alternative accepted. Based on the cointegration test conducted, the study confirmed cointegrating relationship

Long Run and Short Run ECM Results

Dependent Variable: $LSME_t$				
Part A: Long Run Results				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t – Stats	Prob.
MPR_t	-0.1241*	0.0703	-1.7655	0.0880
LQR_t	-0.3178**	0.1518	2.0925	0.0453
LDT_t	0.5361**	0.2365	2.2665	0.0311
C	23.5746	25.8015	0.9136	0.3708
Part B: Short Run Results				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t – Stats	Prob.
$D(LDT_t)$	-0.0107	0.0232	-0.4620	0.6486
$D(LDT_{t-1})$	0.0588**	0.0232	2.5363	0.0188
ECM_{t-1}	-0.1424***	0.0233	-6.1032	0.0000
$R^2 = 0.5443$		Adjusted $R^2 = 0.5092$		

Note: *, ** and *** denote significance at 10%, 5% and 1% level.

Long Run and Short Run ECM Results

Dependent Variable: RSB_t				
Part A: Long Run Results				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t – Stats	Prob.
MPR_t	-0.3168***	0.1083	-2.9236	0.0064
LQR_t	0.3191**	0.1441	-2.2144	0.0348
LDT_t	-0.4260*	0.2385	-1.7858	0.0839
C	-274.3693	1801.433	-0.1523	0.8799
Part B: Short Run Results				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t – Stats	Prob.
$D(LDT_t)$	0.0300	0.0262	1.1478	0.2596
$D(LDT_{t-1})$	-0.0652**	0.0253	-2.5787	0.0147
ECM_{t-1}	-0.0121**	0.0054	-2.2273	0.0331
$R^2 = 0.1653$		Adjusted $R^2 = 0.1190$		

Note: *, ** and *** denote significance at 10%, 5% and 1% level.

between monetary policy rate (MPR), liquidity ratio, loan-to-deposit ratio (LDT), and total deposit money banks' deposit (TBD).

Long Run and Short Run Estimation

Following evidence of long run and short run relationship the study found that monetary policy rate had significant positive impact on total deposit money banks' deposit, negative insignificant impact on credit to private sector, negative insignificant effect on deposit money banks' lending to small and medium enterprise and negative significant impact on broad money supply. It was observed from the analysis carried out that, liquidity ratio had positive and significant impact on total deposit money banks' deposit and broad money supply. Also, increase in liquidity ratio is expected to significantly reduce credit to the private sector and deposit money banks' lending to small and medium enterprises. From the regression result, it was observed that loan-to-deposit ratio had significant positive effect on total deposit money

banks' deposit, credit to private sector and deposit money banks' lending to small and medium enterprises. In contrast, result revealed negative and insignificant relationship between loan-to-deposit ratio and broad money supply.

CONCLUSION

Banking sector regulation will continually be on the front burner in an attempt by the Central Bank of Nigeria to strengthen the banking sector and ensure resilient of the banking sector. Financial intermediation process of deposit money banks remains cardinal for economic growth as the financing of investment activities depends on large extent the ability of banks to mediate between the surplus units and deficit units of the economy. The framework for banking sector regulation differs from country to country. As events unfold, various policies are made to fast track a particular objective by the regulators of the deposit money banks. But the extent to which

banking sector regulation impact on financial intermediation with the use of empirical model appears scanty.

This study examined the impact of banking sector regulation on financial intermediation in Nigeria. The investigation reveals that the banking regulatory tools of monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio and loan-to-deposit ratio had positive and significant impact on total deposit money banks' deposit. Both monetary policy rate and liquidity ratio had positive effect on credit to private sector, while the impact of loan-to-deposit ratio on credit to private sector was positive. The study observed that the determinants of deposit money banks' lending to small and medium enterprises are liquidity ratio and loan-to-deposit ratio. Both monetary policy rate and loan-to-deposit ratio had negative effect on broad money supply, as the effect of liquidity ratio on broad money supply was positive and significant. Although the effect of monetary policy rate, liquidity ratio and loan-to-deposit vary with the proxy of financial intermediation, the study concludes that banking sector regulation is a determinant of financial intermediation in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Resulting from the estimation carried out, the following recommendations were made:

- i. The Central Bank of Nigeria should lower her policy rate in order to make credit cheaper for the private sector and small and medium enterprises. This will ensure growth of the private sector and small and medium enterprises, thereby increasing the volume of deposits with deposit money banks due to improved economic activities.
- ii. The Central Bank of Nigeria should reduce the liquidity ratio in order to facilitate financial intermediation.
- iii. To promote financial intermediation, the Central Bank of Nigeria should increase the loan-to-deposit ratio in order to increase credit to the private sector and small and medium enterprises.

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